

DEVELOPMENT OF A SUSTAINABILITY INDEX FOR ENGINEERING CONSTRUCTION PROJECTS IN UGANDA: A LITERATURE-BASED APPROACH

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Abstract

Uganda's rapid infrastructural growth has heightened the need for sustainable construction practices that align with environmental responsibility and socio-economic equity. Globally, the construction industry is recognized as a major contributor to environmental degradation due to its excessive consumption of energy, natural resources, and the generation of greenhouse gas emissions. In Uganda, the industry remains labour-intensive, inefficient, and associated with high pollution levels, showing the urgency to adopt sustainability-oriented frameworks. However, limited local data and context-specific tools make it difficult to measure and manage sustainability in building projects effectively. This review of literature aimed to support the development of a sustainability index for Uganda's engineering construction sector. The specific objectives guiding the review included: identifying key sustainability attributes relevant to construction projects, analyzing existing models and indices for measuring sustainability in construction projects, and identifying research gaps within the reviewed literature. A structured literature search was conducted using Scopus and Google Scholar databases, focusing on publications from 2015 onward. The search incorporated terms related to sustainability, the construction industry, indices, and low- and middle-income countries. Scopus was selected for its rigorous journal indexing and peer-reviewed coverage, and Google Scholar expanded the scope to include relevant literature and institutional publications. The analysis of the literature review reveals a lack of localized sustainability assessment tools and the fragmented adoption of sustainable practices across construction phases. The review concludes by highlighting that a contextually relevant sustainability index is crucial for guiding policy, benchmarking, and performance measurement in Uganda's construction industry. The findings of this study will contribute to the development of sustainability-oriented frameworks for the construction industry in Uganda and other developing countries.

Keywords: Assessment Tool, Construction Sustainability, Sustainability Attributes, Sustainability Index.

1. INTRODUCTION

As Uganda continues to experience rapid infrastructural growth, the need for a comprehensive sustainability index tailored to engineering construction projects has become increasingly critical to ensure the prioritization of viable projects within limited resources and constraints. According to Uganda's Ministry of Lands, Housing and Urban Development (2023), the construction sector grew by 8.5% in 2022, contributing significantly to Gross Domestic Product (GDP) but also placing increased pressure on natural resources and urban systems.

Globally, the construction industry is responsible for approximately 36% of final energy use and 39% of energy-related carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions, making it one of the most resource-intensive and polluting sectors (United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP), 2022). This sector also consumes about 40% of the over 90 billion tonnes of raw materials extracted annually, contributing to potential shortages and price volatility in raw material supply chains (Valentini, 2023). This unsustainable use of the Earth's resources is eroding the planet's support systems, as the sector remains locked in the 'take-make-dispose model' of high resource consumption and low recovery (Tunji et al., 2018).

Construction activities directly linked to biodiversity loss, land degradation, and climate change (Kaja and Goyal, 2023; Al-Numan, 2024)). In Uganda, data from the National Environment Management Authority (NEMA), (2022) reveals that over 70% of construction firms do not implement environmental management systems, and construction waste accounts for more than 40% of total urban solid waste in Kampala city.

In the context of developing countries, very little is known about the sustainability practices of construction firms (Ullah et al., 2020), which makes it harder to gauge sustainability in the building construction projects. Moreover, Hashemi *et al.*, (2015) and recent assessments by the Uganda Bureau of Statistics (2023) indicate that energy consumption per square meter in Ugandan building construction is 20–30% higher than the Sub-Saharan Africa average. Socially, the construction sector in Uganda employs a large portion of the labor force, often under hazardous conditions.

A study by Kiconco *et al.*, (2019) reports occupational injuries of building construction workers in Kampala-Uganda at 32.4% and highlights the need for sustainable control measures. The construction industry remains vital to a country's economy, with numerous backward and forward linkages to socio-economic development and sustainable infrastructure (Khan *et al.*, 2021). However, sustainable building practices must be adopted for these benefits to be realized. It is estimated that buildings consume about 40% of global energy, generate large volumes of greenhouse gases (GHG), and are significant contributors to global warming (Chhabra and Grover, 2024). By 2035, it is projected that buildings will emit 42.4 billion tons of carbon globally, marking a 43% increase since 2007 (Darko *et al.*, 2017).

In most countries worldwide, the construction industry has been identified as the leading carbon emitter, primarily due to resource-intensive traditional construction methods (Huang *et al.*, 2018). The built environment thus remains one of the most significant contributors to environmental degradation, posing a threat to the safety and well-being of future generations. The contribution of the construction industry to global emissions undermines progress toward environmental sustainability and several other Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) (Fei *et al.*, 2021; Shinwell and Cohen, 2020).

The literature review encompassed the three significant dimensions of sustainability: social, environmental, and economic. The review was guided by the broader research objective of developing a sustainability index for engineering construction projects in Uganda in 2025.

2. METHODOLOGY

The study consists of a literature review that was guided by the objectives of identifying the major attributes of sustainability in building construction projects, examining the various models and indices developed to measure sustainability in the construction industry, and identifying the research gaps in the reviewed articles to develop a sustainability index for engineering construction projects in Uganda.

2.1 Rationale for the review

As Uganda advances its economic development through various interlinked sectors guided by national development models, there is a growing need to ensure that progress aligns with the core principles of sustainability, balancing social, economic, and environmental dimensions. The literature review established a theoretical and empirical foundation to inform the development of a contextually relevant sustainability index for building construction projects in Uganda. This review aimed to examine the global literature and best practices on sustainability within the built environment, identifying key indicators and methodologies that can be adapted to suit the unique conditions of the Ugandan construction sector.

2.2 Approach to the review

The Scopus platform was chosen for its greater journal coverage compared to similar databases. It ensures high-quality peer-reviewed articles and rigorous inclusion criteria and indexing processes, offers access to more recent publications, and provides a reproducible process (Rostamnezhad and Thaheem, 2022).

Fig 1: Pictorial Representation of the Methodology

Search String-The Scopus core collection was searched using the string: (TITLE-ABS-KEY (Sustainability OR Sustainable OR “Eco-friendly” OR Environmental OR Resilient OR “Low-impact”) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY (“construction industry” OR “building sector” OR “infrastructure sector OR “civil engineering industry” OR “built environment industry”) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY (models OR frameworks OR method* OR approaches OR systems OR techniques) AND ALL (indices OR index OR score OR ranking OR measurement OR rating OR metrics OR “key performance indicators”) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY (“low-and middle-income countries” OR “developing countries” OR emerging markets” OR “global south”) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE, ar) AND (LIMIT-TO (PUBSTAGE, “final”) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE, “English”) AND (PUBYEAR >2015))).

Additional search was done using Google Scholar, which provides more inclusive coverage of academic content, including theses, conference papers, preprints, and institutional repositories that may not be indexed in Scopus, and helps minimize publication bias by incorporating a wider range of academic sources (Halevi *et al.*, 2017).

The review of literature was conducted systematically, adopting three key steps: first, identification of the major attributes of sustainability in building construction projects; second, identification of the different models and indices developed to measure sustainability in the construction industry; and third, identification of the research gaps in the reviewed articles.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Sustainable construction refers to the creation and responsible management of a healthy built environment through the application of resource-efficient and ecological principles (Saka and Adegbebo, 2022). This holistic approach encompasses every stage of a building's lifecycle, from initial planning and design to construction, operation, maintenance, renovation, and eventual deconstruction (Omopariola *et al.*, 2024). The goal of sustainable construction is to minimize the social, economic, and environmental impact of buildings by enhancing energy efficiency, reducing waste, conserving water, and utilizing sustainable materials (Liu *et al.*, 2022).

The scope of sustainable construction is broad, integrating strategies and practices designed to achieve sustainability goals. During the planning and design stages, sustainable construction practices include site selection that minimizes environmental disruption, orientation that maximizes natural lighting and ventilation, and the incorporation of green roofs and walls that enhance biodiversity and reduce urban heat island effects (Nguyen and Macchion, 2023).

During the construction phase, sustainable practices include the use of recycled and locally-sourced materials, implementation of waste management plans to recycle and reuse construction debris, and employment of energy-efficient machinery and construction techniques (Kibert, 2016).

Renovation and deconstruction are the final stages of a building's lifecycle in Sustainable construction. Renovation practices prioritize upgrading existing structures to enhance energy efficiency and extend the building's lifespan, thereby reducing the need for new construction and conserving resources (Pons-Valladares and Nikolic, 2020). Deconstruction, as opposed to traditional demolition, focuses on systematically disassembling buildings to recover and reuse materials, minimizing waste sent to landfills and reducing the need for virgin materials (Bertino *et al.*, 2021).

3.1 Major attributes of sustainability in building construction projects.

In any development initiative, sustainability has been regarded as the center of development in meeting the needs of both the current and future generations. Sustainable development has been defined as development that meets the current needs without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs (United Nations, 2025). Regarding this definition of

sustainable development, a project is considered sustainable if it preserves the environment, provides social stability, and promotes economic reforms without compromising cost, time, quality, and performance (Salah *et al.*, 2023). Sustainability can also be defined as the practice of preserving natural resources for future generations (Yılmaz and Bakış, 2015). The goals of sustainability include, but are not limited to, protecting biodiversity and livability while preserving its life-supporting systems, making efficient use of renewable resources, limiting the consumption of non-renewable resources, minimizing environmental harm, and safeguarding historical and cultural sites. Sustainability needs a coordinated, proactive effort, especially for built environments that cannot be developed without the active participation of people in the process (Elmqvist *et al.*, 2019). In the construction industry, three major attributes of sustainability have been emphasized. According to ISO 15392 (2008), construction sustainability includes ‘considering sustainable development in terms of its three primary aspects (economic, environmental, and social), while meeting the requirements for technical and functional performance (as summarized in Figure 2).

Fig 2: Attributes of sustainability

The environmental dimension of sustainability is viewed as having been impacted by the construction industry through high levels of carbon emissions released into the atmosphere and the generation of large volumes of waste in construction projects. Globally, there has been a tremendous increase in the use of natural resources, straining the environment as resources become depleted (Abou Diaz *et al.*, 2019). The environment has been affected through various mechanisms, including the depletion of natural resources, environmental pollution, and rising sea levels (De Laat, 2019; Mubeen *et al.*, 2023)). The building and construction industry contributes to the increase in carbon emissions in many ways. One way is through the manufacturing of raw materials and the transportation of finished products. The cement section alone accounts for 5% of global man-made CO₂ emissions (Abou Diaz *et al.*, 2019). According to the World Business Council for Sustainable Development, building can have significant adverse impacts on the environment, consuming 40% of the total energy, which generates

greenhouse gases (GHG) and appears to be one of the key contributors to global warming (Khan *et al.*, 2021).

As the earth's resources continue to deplete at an alarming rate, there is a pressing need to restructure the global construction industry to mitigate against the rising issues of climate change. To mitigate this issue, researchers have suggested adopting environmentally friendly practices as a means to enhance the environmental sustainability of construction processes, activities, and practices (Singh, 2023).

The submissions of Ullah *et al.*, (2020) describe environmental practices as a set of policies, principles, and strategies that aim to integrate economic considerations with environmental and social concerns to achieve more sustainable and equitable development outcomes. These practices promote sustainable construction, which focuses on designing and constructing buildings that minimize their environmental impact (Iqbal *et al.*, 2021). According to Oke *et al.*, (2019), these practices can be applied to various aspects of construction, such as material selection, waste management, energy efficiency, indoor air quality, transportation, water conservation, and green building design. Thus, by adopting environmentally friendly practices, the construction industry can reduce its negative impact on the environment while delivering high levels of development (Moshood *et al.*, 2024).

Social sustainability in development processes is said to have unique attributes that drive sustainable construction processes. In the recent past, the aspect of social sustainability has been sidelined, with a major focus on both environmental and economic sustainability (Misopoulos *et al.*, 2019). However, in recent developments, social sustainability has been recognized as an integral part of sustainability, as development occurs within people and their communities (Winston, 2022). A publication by the World Bank Group on Social Sustainability in Development highlights that social sustainability increases when more people feel part of the development process and believe that they and their descendants will benefit from it (World Bank, 2023).

The key influencing attributes of social sustainability in building construction have been identified to include health and safety concerns, stakeholder engagement, community well-being, equitable labor practices, and cultural inclusivity. According to Ezeh *et al.*, (2024), increased stakeholder involvement in construction projects leads to a demand for sustainable building materials and practices in construction work. This drives the adoption of sustainable technologies, such as solar panels, green roofs, or rainwater harvesting systems, on construction sites (Pirouz *et al.*, 2021).

Moreover, increased stakeholder involvement in construction projects drives collaboration and innovation in the construction industry. As different stakeholders become more aware of the impact of their actions, they may be more willing to collaborate to find solutions that mitigate unsustainable outcomes in the industry. This may prompt the development of new technologies, materials, and construction methods that are more sustainable and environmentally friendly (Cook and Larsen, 2021; Kadam, 2024). Pressures from stakeholders, including clients, customers, investors, employees, and regulators, can also serve as drivers for the adoption of

sustainable construction practices. For example, clients may be more likely to choose a construction company that is committed to sustainability and has a track record of using environmentally friendly materials and practices. Additionally, investors may be more inclined to invest in companies that prioritize sustainability, as this can be viewed as a sign of responsible management and long-term thinking (Ma *et al.*, 2022). These pressures can encourage companies to adopt more sustainable practices to meet the expectations of different stakeholders and remain competitive.

Community engagement across the construction project is viewed as an important aspect of social sustainability, as it aligns construction projects with the needs and values of local populations (Rathenam and Dabup, 2017). Community engagement is fundamental to the success of sustainable development initiatives. It ensures that development projects are not only environmentally and economically viable, but also socially inclusive and responsive to the needs and aspirations of the local populace (Srinivasan, 2024).

This participatory approach involves the active involvement of community members in decision-making processes, which allows for the incorporation of local knowledge, cultural values, and preferences into the planning and execution of projects. Despite the relative importance of social sustainability in the construction industry context, its adoption remains low in various construction projects, particularly in developing countries, where projects operate within predefined constraints of cost, time, scope, and quality (Kordi *et al.*, 2022). It is also argued that social sustainability is often overlooked in comparison to the environmental and economic aspects of sustainability in building construction projects (Pocock *et al.*, 2016).

Economic sustainability in the built environment has its attributes that drive sustainability in the construction industry. However, Economic sustainability in the construction sector has been less addressed despite its broad applicability in the economy (Alaloul *et al.*, 2022). Economic sustainability focuses on making informed financial decisions that endure beyond the project's lifespan. It involves reducing construction costs, boosting operational efficiency, and investing in durable materials. The goal is to deliver projects that are affordable to build, maintain, and operate without compromising quality or the environment (Tembo *et al.*, 2023).

Alaloul *et al.* (2022) conducted a comparative analysis of the construction sectors in the USA, China, and the UK, highlighting the significant role of economic sustainability in stabilizing and advancing national economies. Their study emphasized the importance of integrating circular economy principles to enhance economic performance and resilience in the construction industry (Alaloul *et al.*, 2022). The concept of a circular economy in construction emphasizes resource efficiency, waste reduction, and material reuse, addressing not only environmental concerns but also offering substantial economic benefits (Hossain *et al.*, 2020).

Literature identifies core components of Economic sustainability to include sustainable procurement processes, energy efficiency, cost management, and technology adoption, among others. In the context of Uganda, adopting economic sustainability practices in construction could lead to significant cost savings and improved project outcomes. Strategies such as modular design, energy modeling, and supply chain optimization have been shown to reduce

expenses and enhance building quality (Goh et al., 2023; Attajer *et al.*, 2025). Given the nexus between the attributes of sustainability in building construction projects, this review conceptualized the interlinkages that exist among these attributes and how they drive sustainability based on the literature reviewed.

Fig 3: Nexus between attributes of sustainability in building construction (conceptualized ideas based on the literature review)

3.2 Different models/indices developed to measure sustainability in the construction industry

Various methodologies have been advanced to construct composite indices that measure sustainability in the construction industry. Michela *et al.* (2005) described a framework for constructing a composite indicator, which includes several steps, with weighting and aggregation being the most significant. The other steps outlined included: selection of indicators and data, imputation of missing data, and normalization of the selected indicators. Furthermore, Bellver-Domingo *et al.*, (2023), considered a standard weight multi-criteria decision analysis-data Envelopment Analysis (MCDA-DEA) approach for constructing indices.

One of the methodologies for constructing a composite sustainability index is illustrated in the figure 4.

Fig 4: A step-by-step process of constructing a composite sustainability index of a construction project

Another framework advanced for assessing sustainability in the building construction industry is the Leadership in Energy and Environmental Design (LEED) rating system, developed by the U.S. Green Building Council (LEED, 2025). LEED evaluates building performance across various categories, including energy efficiency, water usage, material selection, and indoor environmental quality. LEED's adoption has been instrumental in driving sustainable design practices, particularly in North America. As a framework, it addresses everything from energy and water use to materials selection, managing waste, and indoor environmental quality

through a series of credit categories tailored for each rating system. To achieve LEED certification, a project must first complete all prerequisites and then earn points by selecting and satisfying credit requirements. Projects undergo a verification and review process, earning points that correspond to a specific level of LEED certification which is required for them to be declared sustainable (US Green Buildings Council, 2019).

Building Research Establishment (BRE) advanced BREEAM In-Use assessment framework as a means of assessing sustainability in the building construction industry. BREEAM In-Use is designed to evaluate the environmental performance of existing buildings during their operational phase (BRE Global, 2009). The framework is structured into three key sections: Part 1 (asset performance), Part 2 (building management), and Part 3 (occupier management) The three categories are meant to enable comprehensive analysis of various sustainability dimensions within the building projects, that include energy efficiency, water usage, material sourcing, waste management, transport access, and indoor environmental quality (Semanda *et al.*, 2024).

The framework is considered a crucial reference tool for developing sustainability indices in the construction sector, owing to its standardized indicators and measurable scoring methodology (Sharifi and Murayama, 2013). In developing country contexts, BREEAM's flexible scoring system allows for localization of weights and criteria to reflect regional environmental and socio-economic priorities (Alwan and Jones, 2024). This adaptability makes it suitable for informing sustainability performance benchmarks and for constructing context-specific indices. The tool's structured evaluation methodology provides a basis for quantifying building performance, and its results can be aggregated to create composite sustainability scores that align with broader policy or sectoral goals.

Identification of the research gap in the reviewed articles

Table 1: Identification of research gaps in the reviewed articles

Authors	Research study area	Knowledge gap	Recommendation
United Nations (2025); Yılmaz and Bakış (2015)	General definitions and goals of sustainability and sustainable development	Broad definitions provided with limited focus on practical frameworks for implementation in construction	Operationalizing sustainability principles through sector-specific frameworks like green building assessment tools
Salah <i>et al.</i> (2023).	Sustainability attributes in development projects	Lack of integration of sustainability pillars (environmental, economic, social) with project constraints like cost and time	Promoting balanced sustainability planning that aligns sustainability goals with project performance metrics
Abou Zahr Diaz <i>et al.</i> (2019); De Laat (2019); Khan <i>et al.</i> (2021)	Environmental impacts of construction (e.g., CO ₂ emissions, resource depletion)	Over-emphasis on global impacts; limited contextualization in local construction sectors	Encouraging regional studies on emission sources and developing targeted green policies for local industries

Iqbal <i>et al.</i> (2021); Oke <i>et al.</i> (2019) Singh (2023); Ullah <i>et al.</i> (2020)	Environmentally friendly construction practices	Fragmented adoption of sustainable practices across construction phases	Mainstreaming green practices like material reuse, waste reduction, and energy efficiency through policy and incentives.
Ezeh (2024); Cook and Larsen (2021); Ma <i>et al.</i> (2022); Pirouz <i>et al.</i> (2021); World Bank (2023)	Social sustainability and stakeholder engagement	Social aspects are often sidelined in construction project planning	Institutionalizing stakeholder engagement and labor equity as core requirements in construction project frameworks
Srinivasan (2024).	Community engagement in sustainable construction	Community voices often excluded from planning and implementation	Fostering participatory planning processes that incorporate local values and cultural knowledge
Alaloul <i>et al.</i> (2022); Goh <i>et al.</i> (2023) Tembo <i>et al.</i> (2023)	Economic sustainability in construction	Economic sustainability is under-addressed despite potential benefits	Adopting circular economy principles, optimizing supply chains, and investing in cost-effective sustainable technologies
Michela <i>et al.</i> (2005).	Framework for constructing composite sustainability indicators	Lacked focus on construction-specific sustainability applications	Application of the composite index framework with construction-related indicators for industry-specific relevance
US Green Buildings Council (2019)	LEED green building certification system	Primarily applied in high-income regions; limited adaptability in low-resource contexts.	Customizing LEED criteria to fit developing country settings, considering local building norms and resources
BRE Global Ltd. (2009)	BREEAM In-Use framework for sustainability assessment of existing buildings	Limited awareness and application in emerging markets despite its adaptability	Promoting BREEAM In-Use as a benchmarking and index development tool tailored to regional and country priorities

4. CONCLUSION

The reviewed literature shows a growing global consensus on the importance of sustainability in development, with strong foundational definitions provided by key sources (United Nations and ISO standards). However, a consistent gap across the literature is the limited translation of these broad sustainability concepts into practical, context-specific applications within the construction industry, particularly in developing countries. In the past, significant emphasis has been placed on environmental impacts; however, there remains a lack of integration of sustainability's three core pillars (environmental, economic, and social) with traditional construction project constraints (cost, time, and quality). Also, most existing frameworks tend to adopt a global perspective, with minimal consideration for regional environmental

challenges and socio-economic realities. To address these gaps, the literature suggests a strong need for the development of localized sustainability assessment tools and the construction of specific indices that reflect regional priorities and national context. Such efforts would not only enhance the relevance of sustainability frameworks but also support more effective planning, implementation, and monitoring of sustainable construction practices in engineering construction projects.

Author Contributions

A.K. Bazairwe was responsible for the original concept, searching the bibliography, selecting the relevant references, coding the references, drafting the manuscript, analysis. S.K. Makhanu. was responsible supervision, review and editing, validation, conceptualizing the manuscript. M. Mukolwe was responsible for reviewing the work plan preparation and the bibliographic search, conceptualizing the draft, validation and supervision. C. Wamalwa. was responsible for data curation, reviewing the search string, and reviewing the manuscript.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no potential conflict of interest regarding the publication of this work. In addition, the ethical issues including plagiarism, informed consent, misconduct, data fabrication and, or falsification, double publication and, or submission, and redundancy have been completely witnessed by the authors.

Abbreviations

<i>GDP</i>	Gross Domestic Product
<i>CO₂</i>	Carbon dioxide
<i>UNEP</i>	United Nations Environment Programme
<i>ABS</i>	Abstract
<i>Fig.</i>	Figure
<i>GHG</i>	Greenhouse gas
<i>MCDA-DEA</i>	Multi-criteria decision analysis-data Envelopment Analysis
<i>LEED</i>	Leadership in Energy and Environmental Design
<i>U.S.</i>	United States
<i>BRE</i>	<i>Building Research Establishment</i>
<i>BREEAM</i>	Building Research Establishment Environmental Assessment Method.

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